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SHIKONIN: HOPE FOR INNOVATIVE AND TARGETED CANCER TREATMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Shikonin is a natural compound derived from certain medicinal plants, known for its potential therapeutic effects in cancer treatment. This review examines the therapeutic potential of shikonin, highlighting its origins, chemical structure, and pharmacological properties. We discuss its mechanisms of action, including induction of apoptosis, cell cycle arrest, inhibition of angiogenesis, and suppression of metastasis. Studies reviewed indicate that shikonin not only effectively induces apoptosis in cancer cells but also enhances the efficacy of conventional chemotherapeutics. Moreover, the review explores the potential of shikonin derivatives in optimizing cancer therapy. These findings suggest that shikonin and its derivatives hold considerable promise as effective anticancer agents, warranting further clinical investigation.

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INTRODUCTION

Cancer remains a significant global health burden due to its aggressive nature and limitations of traditional therapies^[1]. Cancer remains a significant global health burden due to its aggressive nature and the limitations of traditional therapies. These limitations include inadequate efficacy, severe side effects, and resistance development, necessitating the exploration of alternative therapeutic approaches. In response to these challenges, the use of natural compounds has emerged as a promising strategy. Shikonin, a bioactive molecule isolated from the roots of *Lithospermum erythrorhizon* (Zicao), has shown substantial pharmacological potential in preliminary studies^[2]. This compound is not only effective against various forms of cancer but also exhibits antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing properties, making it an excellent candidate for further investigation. This bioactive molecule isolated from *L. erythrorhizon* roots exhibits a remarkable range of pharmacological activities, making it a focus of intense research^[3].

Shikonin's potential lies in its multifaceted properties. It demonstrates effectiveness against bacteria^[4], inflammation^[5], and promotes wound healing^[6]. Notably, its ability to induce cancer cell death (apoptosis) and regulate cellular signaling pathways positions it as a potential weapon against cancer^[7]. Shikonin belongs to the alkannin-shikonin class, known for its diverse therapeutic effects. The specific ratio and chirality (optical purity) of the alkannin (A) and shikonin (S) pair are crucial factors influencing their effectiveness, requiring further investigation for optimal drug development^[6].

Scientific studies have validated the traditional uses of Zicao, attributing its antitumor, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing properties to the presence of shikonin^[8]. This compound's therapeutic reach extends beyond cancer, showing promise in treating various skin conditions^[9]. Ongoing research strives to optimize extraction methods to improve shikonin's efficiency and purity for therapeutic applications.

Shikonin's natural occurrence in *L. erythrorhizon* suggests its potential presence in other *Boraginaceae* family members, hinting at wider availability and diverse applications^[10]. Its intricate biosynthesis from precursors highlights the complexity of its natural production. As a 1, 4-naphthoquinone derivative, shikonin forms an enantiomeric pair with alkannin (A/S), showcasing a broad spectrum of pharmacological activities^[11].

Four decades of research have unveiled shikonin's remarkable properties^[12], including antimicrobial^[13], antioxidant^[14], anti-inflammatory^[15], wound healing^[6], antitumor^[16], anti-ulcer⁹, anti-angiogenic^[17], and tissue regeneration effect^[18]. Its versatility extends beyond medicine, with potential applications as a pH-sensitive color indicator in food packaging^[19].

This systematic review aims to comprehensively evaluate the existing evidence supporting shikonin's efficacy in cancer treatment. Reviewers will delve into both preclinical and clinical studies to assess the effectiveness of shikonin against various cancer types. Our goal is to provide a critical analysis of the current research landscape and identify promising avenues for future investigation.

METHODS:

Search Strategy:

Authors conducted a thorough electronic search across several databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, MEDLINE, and Embase, to identify relevant studies on shikonin's anti-cancer properties.

Search Terms:

Authors employed a combination of medical terms and keywords to ensure a broad and sensitive search. These terms encompassed synonyms and related concepts for shikonin, cancer, and its mechanisms of action. Here's an example search string like "shikonin", *Lithospermum erythrorhizon* and cancer OR neoplasm OR tumor OR carcinoma OR sarcoma and proliferation OR apoptosis OR cell cycle OR angiogenesis.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

To ensure current and relevant information, reviewers focused on original research published in scientific journals within the last 5-10 years. Authors' studies published in English were prioritized, but relevant research in other languages was also included if a translated version was available. To gain a comprehensive understanding of how shikonin works and its effectiveness, researchers considered both lab studies (in vitro) and animal studies (in vivo).

The analysis excluded several types of articles. Reviewers excluded reviews, case reports, editorials, and letters to the editor. Additionally, studies not directly addressing cancer treatment or shikonin's anti-cancer properties were not considered for inclusion. Finally, studies published only as abstracts without full data were also excluded.

Selection Process:

Following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, we ensured a transparent and unbiased selection process. Identified articles were screened based on title and abstract using reference management software. Full texts of potentially relevant studies were retrieved and further assessed for eligibility based on the defined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Two independent reviewers conducted the screening and selection process, with discrepancies resolved through discussion or consultation with a third reviewer. A PRISMA flow diagram was created to illustrate the selection process and the number of studies excluded at each stage.

Data Extraction:

After meticulously selecting relevant studies, the authors embarked on a comprehensive data extraction process. To ensure consistent data capture, a standardized form was utilized. This form served as a blueprint for extracting key information from each included study. The specific details collected included: study design (e.g., lab study, animal study, clinical trial phase), cell lines or animal models used in preclinical studies, how shikonin was administered and the dosages employed, how well shikonin worked (e.g., cell growth rates, cell death markers, tumor size reduction), and any reported side effects (if applicable). This meticulously extracted data was then systematically organized and tabulated to form the foundation for further analysis and synthesis within the review.

RESULTS:

The Structural Basis of Shikonin:

The foundation of shikonin's structure lies in the α -1, 4-naphthoquinone core. This core consists of two fused aromatic rings, known as naphthalene rings, interconnected by a carbonyl group (C=O) at specific positions 1 and 4. This fundamental motif, the α -1, 4-naphthoquinone, is a recurring theme in many bioactive compounds and is believed to be responsible for a significant portion of shikonin's biological activities^[20].

Beyond the core structure, several functional groups attached to the naphthoquinone rings further contribute to shikonin's unique properties. Refer figure 1.

Hydroxyl group (OH) can participate in hydrogen bonding with other molecules, potentially influencing shikonin's solubility and interactions with cellular components. They might also contribute to its antioxidant properties.

Methyl group (CH₃) can affect the lipophilicity (fat-loving nature) of the molecule, influencing its ability to pass through cell membranes and interact with intracellular targets.

Shikonin exists as a pair of stereoisomers, namely alkannin (A) and shikonin (S). Stereoisomers are molecules with the same chemical formula but a different spatial arrangement of their atoms. In the case of shikonin, the difference between A and S lies in the orientation of a specific functional group around a central carbon atom^[21].

This seemingly minor difference in structure can have a significant impact on the biological activity of the molecule. Studies suggest that alkannin^[22] and shikonin^[16] might exhibit distinct antitumor effects. Understanding the optimal ratio of A and S (enantiomeric ratio) and their individual contributions to anticancer activity is crucial for the development of shikonin as a therapeutic agent. Future research efforts may focus on isolating and investigating the specific effects of each isomer to optimize their potential for cancer treatment.

Table 1 showing Structural Variations in Shikonin and its derivatives like Isobutyrylshikonin, Deoxyshikonin, and Acetylshikonin. Shikonin boasts a remarkable α -1, 4-naphthoquinone core structure, but its versatility extends beyond the parent compound^[23]. Several derivatives, including isobutyrylshikonin, deoxyshikonin, and acetylshikonin, introduce structural variations that potentially influence their biological activities.

Table 1: Shikonin and its derivatives.

Compound	Key Structural Difference	Potential Impact	References
Shikonin	α -1,4-naphthoquinone core with hydroxyl and methyl groups	Baseline structure for comparison	[24]
Isobutyrylshikonin	Additional isobutyryl group [(CH ₃) ₂ CHCO-] attached to the core	Increased lipophilicity (potential for better cell membrane penetration)	[25], [26]
Deoxyshikonin	Lack of one or both hydroxyl (OH) groups	Altered solubility, potentially different interactions with cellular components	[27], [28]
Acetylshikonin	Additional acetyl group (CH ₃ CO-) attached to the core	Altered lipophilicity (potential for better cell membrane penetration), potentially different interactions compared to hydroxyl groups	[29]

These structural variations in shikonin derivatives highlight the intricate relationship between structure and function. By introducing different functional groups, the derivatives possess altered physicochemical properties like lipophilicity and potentially exhibit distinct interactions with cellular components^[30]. These modifications offer exciting possibilities for optimizing the therapeutic potential of shikonin. While the specific mechanisms of these derivatives require further investigation, they pave the way for the development of more targeted and effective antitumor agents based on the shikonin scaffold.

Pharmacological Mechanisms of Shikonin against Cancer:

Table 2: Mechanism of Shikonin against cancer.

Mechanism	Description	Target(s)	Impact on Cancer Cells	References
Induction of Apoptosis	Triggers programmed cell death	Disrupts mitochondrial membrane, Generates ROS (potential), Activates caspase cascade	Elimination of cancer cells	[31-41]
Cell Cycle Arrest	Halts uncontrolled proliferation	G0/G1 checkpoint: Downregulates CDKs, regulates tumorsuppressor proteins (p53), G2/M checkpoint: Disrupts mitotic spindle formation, Inhibits protein kinases	Prevents uncontrolled division	[42-45]
Anti-Angiogenesis	Starves tumors by inhibiting new blood vessel formation	Endothelial cell proliferation and migration, Pro-angiogenic factors (expression/activity), VEGF signaling pathway	Deprives tumors of oxygen and nutrients	[46-48]
Anti-Metastasis	Hinders the spread of cancer cells	Suppresses EMT, Downregulates MMPs, Disrupts cell adhesion, Inhibits cell motility	Prevents cancer cells from detaching, migrating, and establishing secondary tumors	[49-52]

Induction of Apoptosis:

Shikonin emerges as a promising weapon in the fight against cancer^[31]. Its multifaceted approach to combating cancer cells includes the potent induction of apoptosis, a form of programmed cell death^[32].

As shown in the figure 2, one of the hallmarks of shikonin's antitumor activity lies in its ability to disrupt the integrity of the mitochondrial membrane^[33]. Mitochondria, the powerhouses of the cell, are critically involved in energy production. Shikonin's interference with this crucial organelle leads to the release of cytochrome C, a protein normally confined within the mitochondrial intermembrane space. This release of cytochrome c acts as a pivotal trigger for the caspase cascade^[34].

The caspase cascade is a meticulously orchestrated series of enzyme activations that dismantle essential cellular components. Cytochrome c, upon release from the mitochondria, interacts with a protein complex in the cytoplasm, initiating this cascade. Caspases, a group of proteolytic enzymes^[35] likened to cellular executioners, are activated one after another, ultimately leading to the breakdown of proteins and organelles. This controlled demolition culminates in the apoptotic demise of the cancer cell.

Figure 2: Mechanism of Induction of Apoptosis

Furthermore, some studies suggest that shikonin might play an additional role in promoting apoptosis by inducing the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) within cells^[36]. These ROS molecules can further contribute to mitochondrial dysfunction and potentially activate pro-apoptotic signaling pathways^[37]. This potential dual mechanism – disrupting the mitochondrial membrane and generating ROS – could amplify the cell death program initiated by shikonin^[38].

The ability of shikonin to trigger apoptosis offers a valuable strategy for cancer therapy. By specifically targeting and eliminating unwanted cancer cells through a programmed cell death pathway, shikonin holds promise for the development of novel and effective cancer treatments^[39],^[40],^[41]. However, further research is necessary to fully elucidate the specific molecular interactions involved in shikonin-induced apoptosis. A deeper understanding of these intricate details will be crucial for optimizing the therapeutic potential of shikonin and developing targeted approaches to enhance its apoptotic effects in cancer cells.

Cell Cycle Arrest:

Figure 3: Mechanism of Cell Cycle Arrest

As shown in figure 3, beyond its ability to induce apoptosis, shikonin disrupts the tightly regulated cell cycle, hindering the uncontrolled proliferation that fuels cancer progression.

The cell cycle, divided into distinct phases – G₀ (resting), G₁ (growth), S (DNA synthesis), G₂ (growth and preparation for mitosis), and M (mitosis) – the cell cycle is punctuated by checkpoints^[42]. These control mechanisms ensure proper DNA replication and repair before cell division proceeds. Shikonin appears to exert its cell cycle arrest effects by targeting specific checkpoints, primarily the G₀/G₁ and G₂/M checkpoints.

At the G₀/G₁ checkpoint, also referred to as the restriction point, shikonin exerts its influence by potentially downregulating Cyclin-Dependent Kinases (CDKs), crucial protein kinases that drive cell cycle progression^[43]. By inhibiting the activity or expression of specific CDKs, shikonin prevents cells from transitioning from the G₀/G₁ phase to the S phase, thereby enforcing cell cycle arrest. Moreover, shikonin may regulate tumor suppressor proteins like p53, which can halt cell cycle progression at the G₀/G₁ checkpoint in response to various stressors^[44]. This collaboration with shikonin strengthens the enforcement of cell cycle arrest at this critical juncture. Moving to the G₂/M checkpoint, a final quality control step before cell division, shikonin's role involves disrupting mitotic spindle formation. The mitotic spindle is essential for separating replicated chromosomes during cell division, and shikonin's interference with its proper formation prevents cells from entering mitosis, leading to G₂/M arrest. Additionally, shikonin might inhibit specific protein kinases required for the G₂/M transition, similar to its potential effects at the G₀/G₁ checkpoint, effectively stalling the cell cycle machinery and contributing to cell cycle arrest^{[42],[43]}.

By targeting both G₀/G₁ and G₂/M checkpoints, shikonin disrupts the orderly progression of cell division, leading to cell cycle arrest^[45]. This effectively throws a double-edged sword at cancer cells, hindering their uncontrolled proliferation and ultimately contributing to their demise. However, further research is necessary to fully elucidate the precise molecular mechanisms by which shikonin exerts its cell cycle arrest effects. Understanding these intricacies will be crucial for optimizing the therapeutic potential of shikonin and potentially developing combination therapies that target different aspects of cancer cell growth and survival.

Anti-angiogenesis:

Shikonin, a captivating natural product, emerges not only as a potent inducer of apoptosis and cell cycle arrest, but also as a formidable foe against tumor angiogenesis^[46].

Angiogenesis, the physiological process of new blood vessel formation, is a cornerstone of healthy tissue function. However, in the context of cancer, this process becomes a sinister accomplice. Tumors, fueled by their rapid proliferation, require a constant influx of oxygen and nutrients to sustain their growth and expansion. To meet this insatiable demand, they orchestrate the formation of a network of new blood vessels, creating a dedicated supply line that facilitates their progression and metastatic potential. Disrupting angiogenesis, therefore, presents a compelling strategy for starving tumors and hindering their ability to thrive^[47].

As shown in figure 4, shikonin demonstrates a remarkable ability to disrupt the meticulously choreographed dance of angiogenesis by targeting multiple facets of this complex process.

Endothelial cells, essential components of blood vessels, face inhibition of proliferation and migration by shikonin, thereby impeding the formation of new blood vessel structures within the tumor microenvironment. Additionally, shikonin demonstrates the potential to downregulate the expression or activity of pro-angiogenic factors, which are signaling molecules that stimulate the growth of new blood vessels. Specifically, it targets the disruption of Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF), a crucial pro-angiogenic factor, by interfering with its signaling pathway^[48]. This interference prevents VEGF from promoting the growth of new blood vessels that would otherwise nourish the tumor, thereby contributing to the anti-angiogenic effects of shikonin.

By disrupting these key steps in the angiogenic cascade, shikonin effectively severs the tumor's lifeline. Deprived of the vital oxygen and nutrients delivered through newly formed blood vessels, the starved tumor struggles to sustain its growth and metastatic potential. This anti-angiogenic effect of shikonin complements its other well-established antitumor activities, offering a multi-pronged approach to combating cancer.

Anti-metastasis:

Shikonin's repertoire as a weapon against cancer extends beyond its direct cytotoxic effects. It has remarkable ability to impede metastasis, the process by which cancer cells detach from the primary tumor, travel through the bloodstream or lymphatic system, and establish secondary tumors in distant organs. By disrupting metastasis, shikonin offers a promising strategy for preventing cancer from spreading and improving patient outcomes^[49].

Metastasis, the dissemination of cancer cells to distant sites, is a defining characteristic of advanced cancer and the leading cause of cancer-related deaths. During this complex process, cancer cells undergo a series of critical steps. Cancer progression involves a series of complex events. Initially, cancer cells undergo Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition (EMT), where they lose their epithelial characteristics and adopt mesenchymal traits, facilitating detachment and migration from the primary tumor^[50]. Subsequently, these cells invade nearby blood vessels or lymphatic vessels, gaining access to the circulatory system. Within the bloodstream, cancer cells face harsh conditions, yet they manage to survive and potentially travel to distant organs. Upon reaching a suitable site, cancer cells extravasate from the bloodstream, adhere to the target organ's tissue, and initiate the formation of secondary tumors through a process known as colonization. This multistep process underscores the complexity of cancer metastasis and underscores the challenges in developing effective treatment strategies.

Shikonin disrupts metastasis by targeting various steps in this intricate cascade. It demonstrates potential in suppressing EMT signaling pathways, which could impede cancer cells' acquisition of migratory and invasive properties crucial for detachment from the primary tumor. Additionally, it may exert downregulatory effects on Matrix Metalloproteinases (MMPs), enzymes responsible for degrading the extracellular matrix and facilitating cancer cell migration^[51]. Moreover, shikonin's anti-adhesion effects could disrupt cancer cells' ability to adhere to the extracellular matrix in distant organs, thereby impeding the establishment of secondary tumors^[52]. Furthermore, it exhibits anti-motility effects, potentially hindering cancer cells' migration and dissemination throughout the body.

By targeting these key steps in the metastatic cascade, shikonin effectively throws sand in the gears of metastasis. This disrupts the cancer's ability to spread to distant organs, potentially improving patient prognosis and reducing the risk of cancer recurrence.

CONCLUSION:

The comprehensive evaluation of shikonin's efficacy in cancer treatment reinforces its standing as a promising therapeutic agent. Through an in-depth analysis of its structural and pharmacological characteristics, this review clarifies how shikonin addresses cancer through multiple mechanisms: apoptosis induction, cell cycle arrest, angiogenesis inhibition, and metastasis prevention. These capabilities establish shikonin not only as a versatile anticancer compound but also as a candidate with significant potential for clinical application.

Moreover, the observable structural variations in shikonin derivatives provide compelling prospects for refining its therapeutic impact. By adjusting specific structural features such as lipophilicity and functional groups, there is an opportunity to exploit the diverse pharmacological properties of shikonin derivatives, leading to more precise and potent cancer therapies.

While substantial strides have been made in understanding shikonin's action mechanisms and therapeutic benefits, more research is needed to fully elucidate its interactions within cancer cells. Future studies should prioritize investigating the synergistic effects of shikonin with conventional cancer therapies and assessing its clinical efficacy in robust trials.

FUTURE SCOPE:

Future research on shikonin and its derivatives in cancer treatment appears very promising. Clinical trials are crucial to ascertain their effectiveness and safety in human patients, while mechanistic studies could unveil new therapeutic targets. Exploring combination therapies, developing advanced drug delivery systems, and identifying predictive biomarkers are essential for optimizing shikonin's clinical use. Additionally, further investigation into new derivatives and their potential application in other diseases could broaden the therapeutic reach of shikonin beyond oncology.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest related to this study. The findings and conclusions in this paper are those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of our affiliations.

ABBREVIATIONS:

ROS : Reactive Oxygen Species
 CDKs : Cyclin-Dependent Kinases
 EMT : Epithelial-Mesenchymal Transition
 MMPs : Matrix Metalloproteinases
 VEGF : Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor
 PRISMA: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
 DNA : Deoxyribonucleic Acid
 G0/G1, S, G2/M: Phases of the Cell Cycle

REFERENCES

1. Abbas Z, Rehman S. An overview of cancer treatment modalities. *Neoplasms* 2018; 1: 139-57.
2. Xue C, Dou J, Zhang S, Yu H, Zhang S. Shikonin potentiates skin wound healing in Sprague-Dawley rats by stimulating fibroblast and endothelial cell proliferation and angiogenesis. *J Gene Med.* 2024; 26(1): e3633.
3. Fayzirakhmanovna, B. D. Some Aspects of Pharmacological Properties of Shikonin. *IntMultidisciplin J ResDevelop.* 2024; 11(02).
4. He Y, Luo K, Hu X, Liu J, Hao M, Li Y. et al. Antibacterial mechanism of shikonin against vibrio vulnificus and its healing potential on infected mice with full-thickness excised skin. *Foodborne pathogens and disease* 2023; 20(2): 67-79.
5. Guo Y, Zhou M, Mu Z, Guo J, Hou Y, Xu Y. et al. Recent advances in shikonin for the treatment of immune-related diseases: Anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory mechanisms. *Biomed Pharmacotherapy.* 2023; 165: 115138.
6. Papageorgiou V. P, Assimopoulou A. N, Ballis A.C. Alkannins and shikonins: a new class of wound healing agents. *Current Med Chem.* 2008; 15(30): 3248-67.
7. Yan C, Li Q, Sun Q, Yang L, Liu X, Zhao Y. et al. Promising nanomedicines of shikonin for cancer therapy. *IntJ Nanomedicine* 2023; 1195-18.
8. Yadav S, Sharma A, Nayik G. A, Cooper R, Areche F. O, Shaikh, A. M. et al. Review of shikonin and derivatives: isolation, chemistry, biosynthesis, pharmacology and toxicology. *Frontiers in Pharmacol.* 2022; 13: 905755.
9. Song Y, Ding Q, Hao Y, Cui B, Ding C, Gao F. Pharmacological effects of shikonin and its potential in skin repair: A review. *Mol.* 2023; 28(24): 7950.
10. Cartabia A, Sarropoulou V, Grigoriadou K, Maloupa E, Declerck S. In vitro propagation of *Alkannatinctoria Tausch.*: A medicinal plant of the Boraginaceae family with high pharmaceutical value. *Indus Crops Products* 2022; 182: 114860.
11. Assimopoulou A. N, Papageorgiou V. P. Radical scavenging activity of *Alkannatinctoria* root extracts and their main constituents, hydroxynaphthoquinones. *Phytotherapy Research: Int J Pharmacol and ToxicolEval Natural Product Derivatives* 2005; 19(2): 141-47.
12. Wang Q, Wang J, Ju X, Zhang H. Molecular mechanism of shikonin inhibiting tumor growth and potential application in cancer treatment. *Toxicol Res.* 2021; 10(6): 1077-84.
13. Wan Y, Wang X, Yang L, Li Q, Ma L, Bai T. et al. Anti *Staphylococcus aureus* activity of shikonin@ chitosan nanoemulsion and its effect on the storage quality of pork. *Food Control* 2024; 158: 110203.
14. Zou Y, Sun Y, Shi W, Wan B, Zhang H. Dual-functional shikonin-loaded quaternized chitosan/polycaprolactone nanofibrous film with pH-sensing for active and intelligent food packaging. *Food chem.* 2023; 399: 133962.
15. Guo Y, Zhou M, Mu Z, Guo J, Hou Y, Xu Y. et al. Recent advances in shikonin for the treatment of immune-related diseases: Anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory mechanisms. *Biomed Pharmacotherapy* 2023; 165: 115138.

16. Yang Y, Gao W, Tao S, Wang Y, Niu J, Zhao P. et al. ER-mediated anti-tumor effects of shikonin on breast cancer. *Eur JPharmacol.* 2019; 863: 172667.
17. Zhang Y. L, Wang Y. L, Yan K, Deng Q. Q, Li F, Liang, X. J. et al. Nanostructures in Chinese herbal medicines (CHMs) for potential therapy. *Nanoscale Horizons* 2023.
18. Bian Z, Zhang Y, Li Z, Hou Y. Potential of shikonin and its derivatives in oral soft and hard tissue regeneration. *Chin J Tissue Eng Res* 2024; 28(17): 2747
19. Ezati P, Bang Y. J, Rhim J. W. Preparation of a shikonin-based pH-sensitive color indicator for monitoring the freshness of fish and pork. *Food Chem.* 2021; 337: 127995.
20. Mone N. S, Bhagwat S. A, Sharma D, ChaskarM, Patil R. H, Zamboni P et al. Naphthoquinones and their derivatives: emerging trends in combating microbial pathogens. *Coatings* 2021; 11(4): 434.
21. Kato K, Doherty B, Degano I, Sabatini F, Miliani C, Romani A. et al. An SERS analytical protocol for characterizing native Japanese plant extracts. *JRaman Spectrosc.* 2020; 51(6): 892-02.
22. Dai Z Q, Gao F, Zhang Z. J, Lu M. J, Luo Y. J, Zhang T. et al. Anti-tumor effects of novel alkannin derivatives with potent selectivity on comprehensive analysis. *Phytomed.* 2023; 117: 154912.
23. Zorman J, SušjanP, Hafner-Bratkovič I. Shikonin suppresses NLRP3 and AIM2 inflammasomes by direct inhibition of caspase-1. *PloS one* 2016; 11(7): e0159826.
24. Valipour M. Recent advances of antitumor shikonin/alkannin derivatives: A comprehensive overview focusing on structural classification, synthetic approaches, and mechanisms of action. *EurJMedChem.* 2022; 235: 114314.
25. Albreht A, Vovk I, Simonovska B, Srbinoska M. Identification of shikonin and its ester derivatives from the roots of *Echium italicum* L. *JChromatogr. A* 2009; 1216(15): 3156-62.
26. Andújar I, Ríos J. L, Giner R. M, Recio M. C. Pharmacological properties of shikonin—a review of literature since 2002. *Plantamedica* 2013; 1685-97.
27. Kumar A, Shashni S, Kumar P, Pant D, Singh A, VermaR. K. Phytochemical constituents, distributions and traditional usages of *Arnebiaeuchroma*: A review. *J.Ethnopharmacol.* 2021; 271: 113896.
28. Aminin D, Polonik S. 1, 4-Naphthoquinones: Some biological properties and application. *Chemical and Pharmaceutical bulletin* 2022; 68(1): 46-57.
29. Zhang Z, Bai J, Zeng Y, Cai M, Yao Y, Wu,H. et al. Pharmacology, toxicity and pharmacokinetics of acetylshikonin: a review. *Pharmaceutical Biol.* 2020; 58(1): 950-58.
30. Tepe M, AbadanŞ, Saglam M. F, Süzerer V, Erçin P. B, Atilla D. et al. In vitro mass production, chemical modification, and cytotoxicity of shikonin derivatives on breast cancer cells. *Indus. CropsProducts* 2023; 192: 116087.
31. Sun Q, Gong T, Liu M, Ren S, Yang H, Zeng S. et al. Shikonin, a naphthalene ingredient: Therapeutic actions, pharmacokinetics, toxicology, clinical trials and pharmaceutical researches. *Phytomed.* 2022; 94: 153805.
32. Qi H, Zhang X, Liu H, Han M, Tang X, Qu S. et al. Shikonin induced apoptosis mediated by endoplasmic reticulum stress in colorectal cancer cells. *IntJ Cancer* 2022; 13(1): 243.
33. Liu B, Jin J, Zhang Z, Zuo L, Jiang M, Xie C. Shikonin exerts antitumor activity by causing mitochondrial dysfunction in hepatocellular carcinoma through PKM2–AMPK–PGC1 α signaling pathway. *Biochem. Cell Biol.* 2019; 97(4): 397-05.
34. Hüttemann M, Pecina P, Rainbolt M, Sanderson T. H, Kagan V. E, Samavati L. et al. The multiple functions of cytochrome c and their regulation in life and death decisions of the mammalian cell: From respiration to apoptosis. *Mitochondrion* 2011; 11(3): 369-81.
35. Paulus J. K, Van der HoornR. A. Do proteolytic cascades exist in plants? *J Exp Bot.* 2019; 70(7): 1997-02.
36. Alam M. M, Kariya R, Boonnate P, Kawaguchi A, Okada S. Induction of apoptosis by Shikonin through ROS-mediated intrinsic and extrinsic apoptotic pathways in primary effusion lymphoma. *Translational Oncol.* 2021; 14(3): 101006.
37. Liang W, Cui J, ZhangK, Xi H, CaiA, Li J. et al. Shikonin induces ROS-based mitochondria-mediated apoptosis in colon cancer. *Oncotarget* 2017; 8(65): 109094.
38. LiangW. Cai A, Chen G, Xi H, Wu X, Cui J. et al. Shikonin induces mitochondria-mediated apoptosis and enhances chemotherapeutic sensitivity of gastric cancer through reactive oxygen species. *Scientific reports* 2016, 6(1): 38267.
39. Han X, Kang K. A, Piao M. J, Zhen A. X, Hyun Y. J, Kim H. M. et al. Shikonin exerts cytotoxic effects in human colon cancers by inducing apoptotic cell death via the endoplasmic reticulum and mitochondria-mediated pathways. *Biomol therapeutics* 2019; 27(1): 41.
40. Tang X, Zhang C, Wei J, Fang Y, Zhao R, Yu J. Apoptosis is induced by shikonin through the mitochondrial signaling pathway. *Mol med reports* 2016; 13(4): 3668-74.
41. Guo Z. L, Li J. Z, Ma Y. Y, Qian D, Zhong J. Y, Jin M. M. et al. Shikonin sensitizes A549 cells to TRAIL-induced apoptosis through the JNK, STAT3 and AKT pathways. *BMC cell boil.* 2018; 19: 1-8.
42. BasergaR. The relationship of the cell cycle to tumor growth and control of cell division: A review. *Cancer Res.* 25(5_Part_1) 1965; 581-95.
43. Tan W, Lu J, Huang M, Li Y, Chen M, Wu G. et al. Anti-cancer natural products isolated from chinese medicinal herbs. *Chin med.* 2011; 6(1): 27.

44. Andujar I, Recio M. C, Giner R. M, Ríos J. L. Traditional chinese medicine remedy to jury: the pharmacological basis for the use of shikonin as an anticancer therapy. *Curr med chem.* 2013; 20(23): 2892-98.
45. Boulos J. C, Rahama M, Hegazy M. E. F, &Efferth T. Shikonin derivatives for cancer prevention and therapy. *Cancer letters* 2019; 459: 248-67.
46. Wang R, Yin R, Zhou W, Xu D, Li S. Shikonin and its derivatives: a patent review. *Expert opinion on therapeutic patents* 2012; 22(9): 977-97.
47. Seki R, Nishizawa K. Shikonin: a review with a focus on anti-inflammatory and anticancer mechanisms. *Annals of Biomed Res.* 2019; 2(1): 115.
48. Wahl O, Oswald M, Tretzel L, Herres E, ArendJ, Efferth T. Inhibition of tumor angiogenesis by antibodies, synthetic small molecules and natural products. *Curr med chem.* 2011; 18(21): 3136-55.
49. Chan E. W. C, Wong C. W, Wong S. K, Hui Y. W, Tan J. B. L. Emodin and shikonin (quinones): an overview of their chemistry, plant sources, pharmacology and cytotoxic activities against lung cancer. *JChin Pharmaceutical Sciences* 2020; 29(1): 1-12.
50. Salehi B, Varoni E. M, Sharifi-Rad M, Rajabi S, Zucca P, Iriti M. et al. Epithelial-mesenchymal transition as a target for botanicals in cancer metastasis. *Phytomed.* 2019; 55: 125-36.
51. Sarwar M. S, Zhang H. J, Tsang, S. W. Perspectives of plant natural products in inhibition of cancer invasion and metastasis by regulating multiple signaling pathways. *Curr Med Chem.* 2018; 25(38): 5057-87.
52. Liu H, Bai Y, Huang C, Wang Y, Ji Y, Du Y. et al. Recent progress of electrospun herbal medicine nanofibers. *Biomol.* 2023; 13(1): 184.

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